

A close-up photograph of a brown Mysmenidae spider on a textured surface. The spider is positioned in the center-right of the frame, with its body and legs clearly visible. The background is a blurred, light-colored surface with a fine, repeating pattern.

THE MYSMENIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The Mysmenidae, represented by 14 genera, 158 occur throughout the world. Mysmenidae, a small family of minute araneoids are one of the least studied family-level groups of orb weavers, mainly because of their small size and cryptic lifestyle. *Isela okuneana* Griswold, 1985 is the only species named from South Africa. It is a kleptoparasite and has been sampled from the web of the Euagridae spider *Allothelateretis* (Griswold 1985).

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FAMILY MYSMENIDAE

The Mysmenidae, represented by 14 genera and 158 species, occur throughout the world. This small family of minute araneoids are one of the least studied family-level groups of orb weavers, mainly because of their small size and cryptic lifestyle. They belong to the so-called 'symphytognathoid' clade: minute orb weavers that build highly modified orb webs. This clade includes the families Anapidae, Mysmenidae, Symphytognathidae, and Theridiosomatidae (Lopardo & Hormiga 2015). *Isela okuneana* Griswold, 1985 is the only species named from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2021).

COMMON NAME: Spurred orb-weavers

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: Very small (<3 mm). Traditionally, mysmenids can be distinguished by the presence of at least one prolateral claspingspine on the male metatarsus or tibia I, or both; a ventral, subapical, sclerotized spot on the femur of at least leg I on most females and some males, the 'apically twisted' cymbium (Lopardo & Hormiga 2015). Colour varies from yellow-brown to grey, sometimes with greenish tinge, abdomen dark grey with pale markings or white spots. Carapace usually high, with highest point behind eyes; sternum truncated between coxae IV; chelicerae with tiny denticles scattered between cheliceral teeth; labium rebordered; eyes: eight in two rows; anterior median eyes usually larger than other eyes; lateral eyes contiguous, situated close to anterior median eyes; legs with three claws; male with mating spur on metatarsi I; femur I of female with sclerotized spot ventro-subdistally; tarsi longer than or equal in length to metatarsi; tarsi IV without serrated setae; abdomen: soft; spherical to higher than long; usually bearing scattered, long setae; scutum sometimes present.

LIFESTYLE: Mysmenids build highly modified small orb webs but in the Afrotropical Region, mysmenids have mainly been collected from funnel-webs of euagrid spiders which, according to Coyle (1986), can support a wide range of organisms.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. The tiny spiders of the family Mysmenidae are considered to be among the 'least common and most poorly known' of the apneumone spiders (Brignoli 1980).

Isela okuneana male Photo Leon Lotz

Prolateral claspingspine on the male Leg 1

Sclerotized spot on the femur leg 1 of female

Palp with apically twisted' cymbium

GENUS *ISELA* Griswold, 1985

The African endemic genus *Isela* Griswold, 1985 is represented by two species, with only *I. okuncana* known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2021).

COMMON NAME: Isela Spurred orb-weavers

TYPE SPECIES: *Isela okuncana* Griswold, 1985

MORPHOLOGY: Small spiders, 1,4 -1,9 mm in length. Carapace yellow-brown to grey, abdomen dark grey with pale markings, legs yellow-grey; carapace glabrous, with few dorsal and anterior setae; truncate posteriorly, narrowed anteriorly, length highest at thoracic fovea; thoracic fovea indistinct, broadly depressed; anterior eye row recurved; posterior eye row procurved; median ocular quadrangle wider anteriorly; slightly longer than wide posterior median eyes slightly oblong; on tubercle; lateral eyes contiguous, others separate; anterior median eyes larger than the anterior lateral eyes; clypeus concave; chelicerae vertical, length greater than twice clypeal height; retromargin of fang furrow with few teeth and denticles. Abdomen soft; spherical to higher than long; usually bearing scattered, long setae. Leg formula 1423; femur I expanded; male with clasping spines on leg I; female with ventral subdistal sclerotised spot on femora I.

LIFESTYLE: The African *Isela okuncana* is a common kleptoparasite of the Euagridae spider *Allothele teretis* (Griswold 1985).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Isela okuneana male Photo Leon Lotz

Epigyne after Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997)

Isela okuncana female after Griswold (1985)

Isele okuncana Griswold, 1985

COMMON NAME: Spurred Orb-Weaver

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Griswold (1985) from the type locality Mhlopeni Nature Reserve. It is presently known from two provinces (EOO=4 684 km²; AOO=12 km²; 5-895masl.). It was collected on the web of a funnel-web Euagridae (then Dipluridae) spider. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Willowmore Baviaanskloof old gravel pit (-33.65, 24.33). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Tugela River (-29.2202, 31.4796); Mhlopeni Nature Reserve, near Muden (-28.9991, 30.3904); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.4085, 31.4029).

LIFESTYLE: This species is a kleptoparasite living on the curtain web of Euagridae spiders. The webs are typically built in cool, shady areas such as on tree trunks and in holes in stream banks. The species has an obligate kleptoparasitic relationship with its host *Allothele teretis*, and is not very mobile. It is under collected and although the host (*Allothele teretis*) is widespread it has not been confirmed to always be present on their webs. Sampled from the Savanna biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is very small and fragile and should be closely monitored. It is protected in two reserves: Mhlopeni Nature Reserve and Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar -Schoeman 2015) but some more sampling is needed to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Redescribed by Lopardo & Hormiga (2015).

Isele okuncana
Griswold, 1985

Male palp and leg 1 after Dippenaar -Schoeman & Jocqué (1997)

Isele okuncana female and male Photos ASD

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